

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of 1-Aryl-sulphonyl-3-Alkyl/Arylhydantoin as Possible Hypoglycemic Agents: Part III

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Holan and Samuel¹ showed that cyclisation of 1-aryl-3-alkyl-sulphonyl ureas, in the presence of ethyl chloroacetate, led to the discovery of a new series of compounds, 1-aryl-3-alkyl-sulphonyl hydantoins. They further found that the ring closure treatment had no adverse effect on the antidiabetic property of these sulphonyl ureas. In our previous communication, we have reported the preparation of a number of 1-aryl-3-alkyl/aryl-sulphonyl ureas.² Some of these have now been further treated with ethyl chloroacetate in dimethylformamide thereby forming some new 1-aryl-3-alkyl/aryl-sulphonyl hydantoins.

1-Aryl-3-alkyl/aryl-sulphonyl ureas have been prepared by following the method of Das Gupta³ reported earlier.² The compounds synthesised are 1-(2-methyl-3-fluoro) phenyl-4-butyl-, 1-(2-methyl-4-fluoro) phenyl-4-butyl-, 1-(2-fluoro-4'-chloro) phenyl-4-butyl-, 1-(2-methoxy-3-fluoro) phenyl-4-butyl sulphonyl ureas and 1-(2-methyl-3-fluoro) phenyl-4-benzyl-, 1-(2-methyl-4-fluoro) phenyl-4-benzyl-, 1-(2-methoxy-3-fluoro) phenyl-4-benzyl sulphonyl ureas.

Synthesis of 1-Aryl-3-alkyl/aryl-sulphonyl hydantoins.—To a stirred solution of the requisite sulphonyl urea (0.04*M*) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.04*M*) in dimethylformamide (200 ml.) at 80°¹, ethyl chloroacetate (0.04*M*) dissolved in dimethyl formamide (50 ml.) was added slowly. After about two hours, the reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtered solution on concentration left a sticky residue which on treatment with mixed solvents crystallised into fine needles. The compounds synthesised are listed in the Table.

1. Holan, G., and Samuel, E., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4660.
2. Joshi, K. C., and Sengupta, J., *this journal*, 1965, 42, 320.
3. Das Gupta, S. J., *this journal*, 1961, 38, 417.

TABLE I

1-Aryl-Sulphonyl-3-Alkyl/Aryl Hydantoins

Ar.	R	M.P.	Mol. Formula	% Sulphur	
				Found	Calc.
2-CH ₃ -3-Fl-Ph*	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₃ -	112°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ SN ₂ F	9.38	9.75
2-CH ₃ -4-Fl-Ph	"	175°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ SN ₂ F	9.40	9.75
2-Fl-4-Cl-Ph	"	185°	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ SN ₂ Cl	8.89	9.18
2-OCH ₃ -3-Fl-Ph	"	134°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ SN ₂ F	9.00	9.30
2-CH ₃ -3-Fl-Ph	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	145°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ SN ₂ F	8.53	8.83
2-CH ₃ -4-Fl-Ph	"	142°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ SN ₂ F	8.51	8.83
2-OCH ₃ -3-Fl-Ph	"	192°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ SN ₂ F	8.18	8.46

The authors are thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a research fellowship to (J.S.)

Ph = Phenyl

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Received July, 23, 1968

